

Features and usage of computer assisted translation.

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Abstract: *The article views the opportunities of information and communication technologies as a method for soon-to-be interpreters and translators professional motivation formation.*

Keywords: *information and communication technologies, professional motivation.*

At present, in the era of scientific and technological transformations that cover all aspects of modern society, all kinds of technology has become an integral part of a person's daily life; Technical innovations appearing in the world make our life more comfortable and convenient, and production more efficient and economical. There is a growing need for high-quality technical translation of all documentation accompanying this technique, and therefore the use of computer technologies in the translation of technical texts becomes relevant. Computer-Aided Translation (AT) is the translation of texts on a computer using computer technology. It differs from machine translation (MT) in that the entire translation process is carried out by a person, the computer only helps him produce the finished text either in less time or with better quality. Modern translators actively turn to electronic dictionaries (ABBYY Lingvo, Multitran, Translate Google.ru) and special software that helps automate and optimize the translation process. At the same time, it should be borne in mind that specialized translation programs include automated translation systems (Translation Memory class software) and machine translation (or automatic translation), and they must be distinguished. [1]

Thanks to computer technology, it has become possible to carry out large volumes of work efficiently and quickly, speeding up the solution of theoretical and practical problems in many research projects. The technical text is characterized by a number of features that allow the most efficient use of computer technology when translating from foreign language sources of information. First of all, the main stylistic feature of technical texts is an accurate and clear presentation of the material. In technical texts, many expressive means of the language are not used, so as not to violate the basic principle of a technical text - the accuracy and clarity of the presentation of thought. Another feature of the technical text in terms of vocabulary is the extreme

saturation of special terminology, characteristic of this branch of knowledge. Instructions are an example of technical text. In general terms, the instruction can be described as an official business text of technical content. The instruction is a document of official business style. The language design of the instruction text at all levels is characterized by a high degree of standardization, which ensures economy in writing and perception of this type of text. The genre of instructions is represented by different texts: instructions for the use of industrial goods; manuals for the operation of technical means; departmental instructions; job descriptions; annotations to medicines; public instructional texts; useful tips; cooking recipes; prescriptive fragments of educational texts (classifications of instructions are discussed in more detail in our article). The existing variability of instructive texts depends on the sphere of use of the instruction, the situation of instructing and the communicative task of translation. The identification of the text of the instruction and the adequate transmission of information from its text are largely facilitated by the presence of many instructions in relatively free access, presented in different languages. In the practical part, we undertook the translation of a technical text (a fragment of instructions for using a laptop) using the GoogleTranslate program. Google Translate (English Google Translate) is a Google web service designed to automatically translate part of a text or web page into another language. For some languages, translation options are offered to users, for example, for technical terms that should be included in translation system updates in the future. Unlike other translation services such as Babel Fish and AOL, which use SYSTRAN (English) technology, Google, like Translate.ru, uses its own software. Apparently, a self-learning machine translation algorithm is used. The Google translator service also includes the translation of the entire web page and even the simultaneous search for information with translation into another language. For web designers, the company's employees have developed a script that allows you to organize the translation of the site into all available languages. Google Translate, like other automatic translation tools, has its limitations. This tool can help the reader understand the general meaning of the content of a text in a foreign language, it does not provide accurate translations. Work is constantly being done to improve the quality of translation, translations into other languages are being developed. [2]

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